

ENHANCING INSTRUCTIONAL PRACTICES BASED ON THE IDENTIFIED TEACHER'S NEEDS ALONG INNOVATIVE TEACHING STRATEGIES

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Abstract. This research focuses on identifying and addressing teachers' needs in innovative teaching through a quantitative methodology. Surveys, assessments, and classroom observations are used to evaluate educators' proficiency, pinpointing specific areas for improvement. A targeted professional development program is then implemented, incorporating cutting-edge pedagogical techniques. The study quantitatively measures the intervention's impact through post-training assessments, providing insights into the effectiveness of enhanced instructional practices. The research also explores the quantitative correlation between improved teaching methodologies and enhanced student outcomes. The findings aim to inform policymakers, administrators, and teacher training programs, promoting evidence-based strategies for advancing education in the 21st century.

Keywords. Instructional Practices, Innovate Teaching

1 Introduction

This research is rooted in the institution's rich history of producing globally competitive graduates for 77 years since its establishment in 1946. San Carlos College has consistently contributed to various industries by producing competent professionals in education, accountancy, and information technology, and its new program criminology. The success of its graduates is perceived to be intricately tied to the quality of education imparted by the institution, emphasizing the pivotal role of faculty members in shaping the minds of students.

The central focus of this research is on the training of the faculty on the modern innovative teaching strategies that could be used in the teaching-learning activities in the classroom. These innovative teaching strategies are employed in nurturing the intellectual growth of students. Understanding and enhancing this aspect is critical to further elevate the standard of education offered by San Carlos College. The aim is to identify the existing innovative teaching strategies implemented by the faculty, assess their effectiveness, and pinpoint areas that may require improvement.

In recognizing the dynamic nature of education and the evolving needs of students, it becomes imperative to constantly evaluate and enhance teaching methodologies. This research aligns with San Carlos College's mission of providing students not only with academic knowledge but also with essential life skills and Christian values. The institution aims not only to equip students with technical competence but also to nurture their holistic development.

By conducting this research, San Carlos College demonstrates its commitment to continuous improvement and a forward-thinking approach to education. The findings of this study will serve as a foundation for faculty development initiatives, ensuring that educators are equipped with the latest and most effective teaching strategies. Ultimately, the goal is to create an enriched learning environment that aligns with the institution's mission, preparing students not only for academic success but also for a life characterized by competence, values, and a global perspective. This research is a testament to San Carlos College's dedication to maintaining its legacy of producing graduates who are not only academically proficient but also well-rounded individuals prepared for the challenges of the modern world.

1.1 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for the research provides a conceptual foundation that guides the study. It serves as a lens through which the research questions are examined and helped in interpreting the findings. The framework draws on key educational theories and concepts that are relevant to understanding teaching and learning in the context of San Carlos College.

- a. The theoretical underpinning of Constructivism emphasizes that learners actively construct knowledge by integrating new information with existing cognitive structures. This framework acknowledges that innovative teaching strategies should align with constructivist principles, encouraging faculty members to create learning experiences that actively engage students in the learning process.
- b. Experiential Learning Theory is based on the idea that learning is a process of reflection on experience, this theory can be applied to professional development for teachers. Identifying and addressing teachers' needs involves creating opportunities for reflective practice and experiential learning.

1.2 Conceptual Framework

In the quest to enhance instructional practices, the conceptual framework operationalizes the two foundational educational theories: Constructivism and Experiential Learning. These theories act as guides, providing a cohesive and integrated approach to understanding and addressing the diverse needs of teachers within the dynamic landscape of innovative teaching strategies.

At the core of the framework lies Constructivism, which underscores the active role of educators in constructing their understanding. In the context of professional development, this theory asserts that teachers, as perpetual learners, play a central role in identifying and addressing their instructional needs. Aligned with constructivist principles, this approach encourages teachers to tailor their instructional methods to meet individual needs. This adaptive process not only cultivates a more engaging learning experience for educators but also enriches the efficacy of their pedagogical practices.

Complementing Constructivism, the Experiential Learning Theory suggests that learning is a reflective process rooted in experiences. In the context of professional development for teachers, this theory suggests that identifying and addressing needs should encompass creating opportunities for reflective practice and experiential learning. Through active engagement in reflective processes, teachers gain insights into their instructional practices, enhancing their ability to apply innovative teaching strategies in meaningful and contextually relevant ways.

The framework comprises two interwoven components that synergistically guide the elevation of instructional practices; Conducting thorough assessments to pinpoint specific challenges and requirements faced by teachers in the implementation of innovative teaching strategies and designing professional development interventions that are meticulously crafted to align with identified needs, embracing the constructivist ethos of personalized and adaptive learning experiences.

1.3 Research Paradigm

The research paradigm shows the Independent Variable which is the Training Needs Assessment (TNA) and the dependent variable Innovative Teaching Strategy.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

What innovative teaching strategy can be proposed for the teachers' training based on the Training Needs Assessment (TNA) results?

2 Review of Related Literature

In the pursuit of advancing academic practices and identifying the specific needs of educators in innovative teaching strategies at San Carlos College, a thorough exploration of related literature delves into pivotal areas of innovative pedagogy, faculty development, and institutional initiatives in higher education.

The literature consistently emphasizes the transformative impact of innovative teaching strategies on student engagement and learning outcomes. Hendarwati et al. (2021) showcase the effectiveness of active learning methodologies, including collaborative learning and problem-based approaches, in cultivating deeper understanding and critical thinking among students. Moreover, Dela Rosa's work (2016) underscores the advantages of technology integration, illustrating how digital tools can enrich classroom experiences and better prepare students for an increasingly technology-driven world.

A substantial body of literature concentrates on the vital role of faculty development programs in empowering educators to embrace innovative teaching practices. Padillo et al.'s study (2021) scrutinizes the quality of instruction and professional development activities where it determined teachers' teaching competencies and perception of their professional development activities, issues, and concerns. Furthermore, it delves into the significance of ongoing, personalized faculty development, stressing the need for tailored programs that address individual teaching needs.

Recognizing the unique needs of faculty members is imperative in designing effective development programs. Sulasula's research (2023) explores methodologies for faculty needs assessment, underscoring the value of surveys and interviews in uncovering challenges and preferences. Alsaleh's study (2020) delves into the nuances of assessing faculty needs across diverse academic disciplines, offering insights into the variability of instructional requirements.

A prominent theme in the literature centers around aligning faculty development initiatives with institutional missions and goals. OECD (2016) investigates successful cases of institutions integrating technology in innovative teaching practices into their mission, highlighting the interconnectedness of institutional culture and effective pedagogy. As technology assumes an increasingly pivotal role in education, the benefits and challenges of technology integration in the classroom. Additionally, how the strategic use of digital tools can enhance student learning experiences, providing valuable insights into best practices for incorporating technology into innovative teaching strategies. With these, the challenges and opportunities in aligning faculty development programs with an institution's broader vision for educational excellence.

Finally, the literature on the impact of innovative teaching strategies on student learning outcomes is strong. Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) synthesize findings from multiple studies, demonstrating a positive correlation between faculty development in innovative practices and improved student success. Furthermore, it provides evidence of sustained positive effects on student engagement and academic achievement resulting from faculty development initiatives.

In summation, this comprehensive review of related literature establishes a strong foundation for the study at San Carlos College. It underscores the interconnectedness of innovative teaching strategies, faculty development, and institutional goals, emphasizing the necessity for targeted programs that address the unique needs of faculty members while aligning with the institution's mission for educational excellence.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study employed a descriptive method of research to comprehensively identify teachers' needs along with innovative teaching strategies at San Carlos College. This approach allows for a nuanced understanding of the impact of the faculty development programs themselves, comprising workshops, seminars, and initiatives aimed at enriching educators' skills and knowledge in innovative teaching strategies.

3.2 Research Subjects

The respondents consist of faculty members at San Carlos College who engaged in a self-assessment on innovative teaching strategies.

3.3 Data Collection Instrument

A survey questionnaire was disseminated to faculty members to assess their needs related to innovative teaching strategies.

3.4 Statistical Treatment of Data

Average weighted was used to determine the needs of teachers along with innovative teaching strategies. Results will be interpreted using a 4-point Likert Scale:

4	3.50 – 4.00	Highly Needed
3	2.50 – 3.49	Needed
2	1.50 – 2.49	Less Needed
1	1.00 – 1.49	Not Needed

Innovative Teaching Strategy	AWM	DE
Utilize adaptive learning platforms that adjust content and pace based on a student's performance, providing targeted instruction, adapting to individual progress, and addressing gaps in understanding.	1.40	Not Needed
Have students maintain digital journals or blogs that encourage them to use technology, enable multimedia integration, and allow easy sharing and commenting among peers.	2.30	Less Needed
Assign project-based tasks that align with the curriculum, allowing students to delve into real-world applications of the content that promote critical thinking, creativity, and self-directed problem-solving while connecting theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios.	3.80	Highly Needed
Integrate digital tools for students to create interactive and multimedia-rich stories that expand creativity beyond traditional writing, incorporate technology skills, and allow for a more dynamic storytelling experience.	3.60	Highly Needed
Create interactive displays or exhibits showcasing students' work and discoveries. Exhibiting and sharing learning achievements, fostering a sense of pride, and encouraging a culture of sharing.	3.80	Needed
Present students with real-world problems or scenarios that require investigation and solutions that promote deep learning, critical thinking, and application of knowledge in authentic contexts.	2.80	Less Needed
Assign each group a research topic and have them investigate, synthesize information, and present their findings to the class.	2.00	Less Needed
Explore opportunities for cross-grade peer tutoring, where older students mentor younger ones. This creates a sense of responsibility and fosters positive role modeling.	2.00	Less Needed
Design scenarios that are relevant to the learning objectives. These scenarios can be based on real-world situations or hypothetical scenarios that address specific social issues or interpersonal dynamics.	1.80	Less Needed
Conduct experiments in science, technology, engineering, and math (STEM) subjects to provide students with hands-on experiences and a deeper understanding of concepts.	2.20	Less Needed
	2.55	Needed

4 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

4.1 Interpretation of Data

The data-driven evaluation of San Carlos College's teachers' needs regarding innovative teaching strategies reveals a clear consensus on the urgent demand for transformative pedagogical approaches. Project-based learning stands out prominently, securing the highest rating of 3.80 on the scale. This underscores a strong desire among educators to integrate real-world applications into the curriculum, fostering critical thinking, creativity, and self-directed problem-solving. The parallel emphasis on digital tools for interactive storytelling (3.60) and the creation of displays showcasing student work (3.60) reinforces the need for technology-enhanced strategies, highlighting a collective objective to infuse creativity and foster a culture of pride and knowledge sharing.

The overall average score of 2.55 positions these strategies as "Needed," indicating a general acknowledgment of the importance of innovative methodologies in instructional practices. While slightly lower-rated, real-world scenarios (2.80), STEM experiments (2.20), and collaborative initiatives such as group research projects (2.00) and cross-grade peer tutoring (2.00) remain notable. This suggests a holistic approach, recognizing the value of authentic contexts, hands-on experiences, and peer collaboration.

The lower-rated strategy of designing scenarios relevant to learning objectives (1.80) doesn't diminish its significance; instead, it signals a nuanced understanding of the need for scenarios that address social issues and interpersonal dynamics. This comprehensive data offers valuable insights for San Carlos College, providing a roadmap for tailored professional development initiatives. It not only validates the educators' keen interest in embracing innovative teaching strategies but also sets the stage for a dynamic learning environment that aligns with the evolving needs of both faculty and students.

4.2 Interpretation of Data

The implications drawn from the data on San Carlos College's teachers' needs in innovative teaching strategies are profound and carry far-reaching significance for the institution's educational landscape. The resounding call for project-based learning, digital integration, and interactive displays suggests a collective recognition of the transformative power of these approaches. The high rating for project-based tasks (3.80) signals a strong desire to bridge the gap between theory and real-world applications, fostering critical thinking and creativity. Simultaneously, the emphasis on digital tools (3.60) and interactive displays (3.60) underscores an acknowledgment of the pivotal role technology plays in enhancing student engagement and knowledge-sharing culture.

The overall average score of 2.55 falling in the "Needed" category reflects a balanced perspective, showcasing a willingness to explore various innovative strategies. The lower-rated but still significant components, such as real-world scenarios (2.80), STEM experiments (2.20), and collaborative initiatives (group research projects and cross-grade peer tutoring, both at 2.00), collectively advocate for a multifaceted approach to teaching. This suggests that while certain strategies may be in higher demand, there is an appreciation for a diverse set of methods that cater to different learning styles and objectives.

Furthermore, the data implies that professional development initiatives tailored around these innovative strategies could be highly impactful. Educators at San Carlos College may benefit from training programs that equip them with the skills and confidence to seamlessly integrate technology, real-world scenarios, and collaborative learning into their instructional practices. In essence, the implications drawn from this data not only validate the institution's commitment to embracing innovation but also provide a strategic roadmap for fostering a dynamic, engaging, and future-ready learning environment.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the identified needs of teachers at San Carlos College and the implications drawn from the data, several key recommendations emerge to enhance instructional practices and foster a culture of innovation. First and foremost, the institution should prioritize professional development programs that empower educators with the skills and knowledge to effectively integrate project-based learning, digital tools, and interactive displays into their teaching methods. These initiatives should be designed to cater to diverse learning styles, ensuring that educators can adapt these strategies to their specific classroom contexts.

To address the high demand for project-based learning (3.80), San Carlos College may consider facilitating collaborative workshops and seminars where teachers can share best practices, lesson plans, and success stories related to project-based tasks. Additionally, creating a resource hub with curated digital tools and multimedia platforms can support teachers in implementing interactive storytelling and multimedia-rich projects, aligning with the expressed interest in digital tools (3.60).

Recognizing the importance of technology and multimedia integration, the institution should invest in updating technological infrastructure and providing access to relevant software tools. This could include training sessions on digital journal creation, blog maintenance, and the use of multimedia software, supporting educators in implementing strategies like maintaining digital journals (2.30) and creating interactive displays (3.60).

To address the slightly lower-rated strategies, such as real-world scenarios (2.80), STEM experiments (2.20), and collaborative initiatives (2.00), San Carlos College may consider targeted initiatives. This could involve establishing interdisciplinary teams to design and implement real-world scenarios that align with learning objectives, creating a dedicated space for STEM experiments, and promoting cross-grade peer tutoring programs.

In conclusion, these recommendations aim to create a supportive environment that not only acknowledges the identified needs but also provides educators at San Carlos College with the tools and support required to seamlessly integrate innovative teaching strategies into their classrooms. By investing in professional development, technological resources, and collaborative initiatives, the institution can foster a culture of innovation that aligns with the evolving needs of both educators and students.

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